

Comparison of four methods of computing confidence intervals for a proportion

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Contents

Summary	1
Results	2
Comparing confidence interval bounds returned by the various methods	6
Appendix: R code	17

Summary

We compare four methods of computing confidence intervals for a proportion. These four methods are

- the Normal approximation method,
- the Wilson score method,
- the Wilson score method with continuity correction
- the Clopper-Pearson method.

They are described on the Wikipedia page *Binomial proportion confidence interval*.

We estimate the coverage for the various methods listed above for an intended nominal coverage of $\alpha = 0.05$ for various sample sizes n and various probabilities p . We do so with Monte Carlo simulations with 10^6 replicates per combination of parameters (n, p) . The Normal approximation fails to achieve the nominal coverage for small sample size, more so when the true p is close to 0 (or 1). The three other methods are more accurate. We note that the Wilson score method with continuity correction and the Clopper-Pearson method tend to be a bit conservative for small n or p .

Results

Normal approximation

Wilson score method (no correction)

Wilson score with continuity correction

Clopper-Pearson method

Comparing confidence interval bounds returned by the various methods

Normal
Sample size= 20 , p= 0.01

Wilson

Wilson cc

CP

Normal
Sample size= 20 , p= 0.05

Wilson

Wilson cc

CP

Normal
Sample size= 200 , p= 0.1

Wilson

Wilson cc

CP

Normal
Sample size= 1000 , p= 0.001

Wilson

Wilson cc

CP

Appendix: R code

```
## en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Binomial_proportion_confidence_interval

## functions to compute CI for a proportion
CI_prop = function(x ,
                   alpha = 0.05, # 1-(nominal coverage)
                   method=c("normal","Wilson","Wilson_cc","CP"))
{
  CI_normal = CI_Wilson = CI_Wilson_cc = CI_CP = NULL
  p.hat = x/size
  if("normal" %in% method)
  {
    z = qnorm(p=1-alpha/2)
    delta = z* sqrt(p.hat*(1-p.hat)/size)
    CI_normal = cbind(p.hat-delta,p.hat+delta)
  }
  if("Wilson" %in% method)
  {
    z = qnorm(p=1-alpha/2)
    delta = z* sqrt(p.hat*(1-p.hat)/size + z^2/(4*size^2))
    CI_Wilson = cbind((p.hat + z^2/(2*size) - delta)/(1+z^2/size),
                      (p.hat + z^2/(2*size) + delta)/(1+z^2/size))
  }
  if("Wilson_cc" %in% method)
  {
    z = qnorm(p=1-alpha/2)
    delta = z* sqrt(p.hat*(1-p.hat)/size + z^2/(4*size^2))
    CI_Wilson_cc = cbind((p.hat + z^2/(2*size) - delta)/(1+z^2/size),
                          ((p.hat + z^2/(2*size) + delta)/(1+z^2/size)))
  }
  if("CP" %in% method)
  {
    lb = qbeta(p=alpha/2,shape1=x , shape2 = size-x+1)
    ub = qbeta(p = 1-alpha/2, shape1 = x+1 , shape2 = size-x)
    CI_CP = cbind(lb,ub)
  }
  return(list(CI_normal=CI_normal,
              CI_Wilson=CI_Wilson,
              CI_Wilson_cc=CI_Wilson_cc,
              CI_CP=CI_CP))
}
```

```

## function to estimate coverage of CI by Monte Carlo simulation
## Normal approximation method
coverage_normal = function(size, #sample size
                           prob, # actual proportion
                           rep, # number of Monte Carlo replicates
                           alpha = 0.05 # 1-(nominal coverage)
)
{
  X = rbinom(size=size,prob=prob,n=rep)
  p.hat = X/size
  z = qnorm(p=1-alpha/2)
  delta = z* sqrt(p.hat*(1-p.hat)/size)
  mean((prob > p.hat-delta) &
       (prob < p.hat+delta ))
}

## function to estimate coverage of CI by Monte Carlo simulation
## Wilson score method

coverage_Wilson = function(size, #sample size
                           prob, # actual proportion
                           rep, # number of Monte Carlo replicates
                           alpha = 0.05 # 1-(nominal coverage)
)
{
  X = rbinom(size=size,prob=prob,n=rep)
  p.hat = X/size
  z = qnorm(p=1-alpha/2)
  delta = z* sqrt(p.hat*(1-p.hat)/size + z^2/(4*size^2))
  mean((prob > (p.hat + z^2/(2*size) - delta)/(1+z^2/size)) &
       (prob < (p.hat + z^2/(2*size) + delta)/(1+z^2/size)))
}

## function to estimate coverage of CI by Monte Carlo simulation
## Wilson score with continuity correction method
coverage_Wilson_cc = function(size, #sample size
                              prob, # actual proportion
                              rep, # number of Monte Carlo replicates
                              alpha = 0.05 # 1-(nominal coverage)
)

```

```

{
  X = rbinom(size=size,prob=prob,n=rep)
  p.hat = X/size
  z = qnorm(p=1-alpha/2)

  delta = z*sqrt(z^2 - 1/size + 4*size*p.hat*(1-p.hat) + (4*p.hat-2)) + 1
  lb = (2*size*p.hat+z^2 - delta) / (2*(size+z^2))
  subs = lb < 0
  lb[lb < subs] = 0

  delta = z*sqrt(z^2 - 1/size + 4*size*p.hat*(1-p.hat) - (4*p.hat-2)) + 1
  ub = (2*size*p.hat+z^2 + delta) / (2*(size+z^2))
  subs = ub > 1
  ub[sub] = 1
  mean((prob > lb) & (prob < ub))
}

## function to estimate coverage of CI by Monte Carlo simulation
## Clopper-Pearson method
coverage_CP = function(size, #sample size
                        prob, # actual proportion
                        rep, # number of Monte Carlo replicates
                        alpha = 0.05 # 1-(nominal coverage)
)
{
  X = rbinom(size=size,prob=prob,n=rep)
  # F = qf(p=alpha/2 , df1=2*X , df2=2*(size-X+1))
  # lb = 1/(1+ (size-X+1) / (X*F))
  # F = qf(p=1-alpha/2 , df1=2*(X+1), df2 = 2*(size-X) )
  # ub = 1/(1+ (size-X) / ((X+1)*F) )
  lb = qbeta(p=alpha/2,shape1=X , shape2 = size-X+1)
  ## lb2 = 1 - qbeta(p=1-alpha/2,shape2=X , shape1 = size-X+1) # just checking SAS formula p.7 OK
  ub = qbeta(p = 1-alpha/2, shape1 = X+1 , shape2 = size-X)
  ## ub2 = 1- qbeta(p = alpha/2, shape2 = X+1 , shape1 = size-X) # just checking SAS formula p.7 OK
  mean((prob > lb) & (prob < ub))
}

```